

VARIABLE STIFFNESS ACTUATOR FOR ACHIEVING 3D MOVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Across various industries, robotics is rapidly transforming how we work and interact with the world around us. These machines, often inspired by biology or mimicking human movement, can perform tasks ranging from delicate assembly to hazardous exploration. From the factory floor to surgical suites, robots are pushing the boundaries of automation and innovation, with applications that continue to expand and evolve. The innovations for robots in agriculture mostly come in the form of big machines for arable field cultivation. Their significance is high as they can be operated by one operator which is important due to the declining workforce in the agricultural field. Besides the arable fields, harvesting fruits in orchards is one of the biggest and the most labour-intensive tasks. In [1] authors proposed a solution for orchard harvesting that uses a robotic arm. Wang et al. [2] proposed a solution for a soft gripper for harvesting delicate fruits. Another type of solution is proposed by Fei and Vougioukas [3] that uses a moving platform for optimal placement of people for harvesting fruit. Zhao et al. [4] proposed a compliant Stewart-like platform. The platform uses electromagnetic springs that provide variable stiffness which provides compliant property. Some solutions have variable stiffness actuators [5], where controlled impedance change adjusts the stiffness. While these solutions offer promise, they face limitations. The high cost and rigidity of some systems, like those using electromagnetic springs [4], pose challenges for practical implementation. Additionally, robotic arms, though offering precise manipulation [1], lack safety features for working alongside humans. By analyzing these approaches, we can see that current solutions for orchard automation often rely on robotic arms for fruit manipulation. However, the safety concerns associated with robotic arms working near humans necessitate alternative approaches.

In this contribution, we are proposing a solution for a variable stiffness actuator, that provides passive compliance for safe operation alongside humans. By using springs as a compliant component and by applying load that is offset from the spring axis we can control spring stiffness as well as use it as a compliant part for shock absorption in case of collision. So far, our solution is purely mechanical. It uses its mass as well as additional spring pretension to achieve variable stiffness. When driven with precise motor movement, it can achieve kinematics like the Stewart platform while still providing compliance. Depending on the load and use case of the actuator

spring stiffness can be easily adjusted either by swapping springs or by pre-tensioning the springs. This actuator's default movement is linear. However, by attaching a suitable rotational joint to the end of the output shaft, we can achieve rotational movement with a linear component. With three actuators placed in a parallel configuration, a Stewart-like platform 3D movement can be achieved.

By incorporating compliant actuation and carefully designed joints, we can create a versatile actuator suitable for agricultural robotics. This actuator can operate safely alongside humans and handle delicate fruits like apples and peaches without risk of damage. This design would ensure smooth, controlled movements while maintaining structural integrity. We utilized SolidWorks for modelling and will showcase the results of simulations alongside some of the design features.

Figure 1. Schematics of the kinematic model for a rotating module within a Stewart platform-like mechanism with compliant actuation

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